

Microwave-assisted novel stereoselective synthesis of bis- β -lactams with 2,7-phenanthrenyl imines

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Microwave-induced stereoselective synthesis of novel bis- β -lactams substituted at the 2,7 position of the phenanthrene has been performed via ketene-imine [2+2] cycloaddition reaction.

Keywords: New β -lactams, stereoselective, microwave, Schiff base, phenanthrenyl amine, cycloaddition, regioselectivity.

Introduction

Microwave-induced reactions are widely used for the preparation of numerous organic compounds¹. A rapid acceleration of reaction rate is observed in many chemical reactions. As a result, microwave-induced chemistry has become extremely useful in chemistry and science. Stereoselective synthesis of organic compounds is one of the most important targets and challenges to the chemists. Despite progress in microwave-induced reactions, an effective stereochemistry control of products by this method has not been investigated systematically. We are one of the pioneers in studying microwave-mediated reactions and β -lactam chemistry. In our previous work, we have explored stereoselective synthesis and *in vitro* evaluation of diverse β -lactams as antitumor agents²⁻⁴. In continuation of our previous work, we report stereoselective synthesis of two novel isomeric bis- β -lactams derived from 2,7-disubstituted phenanthrene following microwave-induced method. The most important part of this work is that both isomeric β -lactams are prepared by this method at -78°C and 50°C . Thus, it is possible to control the stereochemistry of the β -lactams by changing the conditions of the experiments. Re-

action at -78°C in domestic microwave oven is not investigated.

Results and discussion

Bismuth nitrate is successfully used for several chemical transformations by our group. For example, bismuth nitrate-mediated electrophilic nitration of aromatics was performed⁵⁻⁷. During the course of this investigation, microwave-induced bismuth nitrate impregnated clay was used to nitrate dihydrophenanthrene (**1**) and this reaction afforded 2,7-dinitro derivative (**2**) regioselectively (Scheme 1).

The dinitro compound **2** was then converted to the diamino compound (**3**). This had happened because of oxidative dehydrogenation reaction in the presence of 10% Pd/

Scheme 1. Synthesis of polycyclic aromatic diamine.

C and hydrogen gas.

The diamino compound **3** on reaction with benzaldehyde in toluene at high temperature produced the imine **4** in quantitative yield. Domestic microwave-induced reaction of the imine **4** was performed with acetoxy acetyl chloride (2 equivalents) in the presence of triethylamine at -78°C in dichloromethane for 1 h and the *cis* β -lactam **6** was produced in 70% yield (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2. Synthesis *cis*-3-acetoxy-2,7-phenanthryl bis- β -lactam via Staudinger ketene-imine [2+2] cycloaddition reaction.

In contrast, a similar reaction at 50°C using medium power level (4-5 min) produced the isomeric *trans* compound **7** (Scheme 3). The *cis* and *trans* stereostructures of the β -lactam rings was determined from the NMR data. A coupling constant of 4.92 and 5.1 Hz at C_3 and C_4 positions indicates *cis* β -lactam **5** and a coupling constant 1.6 and 1.7 Hz confirms *trans* compound **7**^{8,9}.

The results described above are fascinating considering that the stereochemistry of novel β -lactam derivatives can

Scheme 3. Synthesis of *trans*-3-acetoxy-2,7-phenanthryl bis- β -lactam via Staudinger ketene-imine [2+2] cycloaddition reaction.

be controlled using domestic microwave oven. The success of low temperature microwave-mediated reaction to *cis* β -lactam indicates that it is not the temperature that is responsible for the acceleration of the reaction rate. The same reaction outside the microwave oven at -78°C for 1 h failed to produce the product even with 10% yield and most of the imine was recovered unchanged. The *cis* β -lactam could not be isomerized to thermodynamically more stable *trans* β -lactam in the presence of triethylamine under microwave irradiation at 50°C . This supports that β -lactam formation reaction in a microwave oven follows two pathways¹⁰.

Conclusion

A facile microwave-induced preparation of two isomeric new β -lactams obtained from novel phenanthryl imines is realized in good yield. The formation of the *trans* isomer is predominantly favored at relatively high temperature whereas formation of the *cis* compound is favored at low temperature. The reaction takes more than 24 h to complete under conventional method at room temperature. Moreover, under conventional method a mixture of isomeric β -lactams are formed. This method described herein is new since controlling stereochemistry of important biologically active molecules is a challenge. The products are unique because no synthesis of these types of molecules except our group was even attempted.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in a Fisher Scientific electrochemical Mel-Temp* manual melting point apparatus (Model 1001) equipped with a 300°C thermometer. FT-IR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Alpha modular Platinum-ATR FT-IR spectrometer with OPUS software, using the samples directly (neat) without making pellets. ^1H NMR (600 MHz) and ^{13}C NMR (150 MHz) spectra were obtained at room temperature with Bruker superconducting UltrashieldTM Plus 600 MHz NMR spectrometer with central field 14.09 Tesla, coil inductance 89.1 Henry and magnetic energy 1127.2 kJ using CDCl_3 or DMSO as solvent. Dihydrophenanthrene (reagent grade, 98%) purchased from TCI Chemicals was used. All other chemicals were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Corporation (analytical grade). Throughout the project the solvents were purchased from Fisher-Scientific. Deion-

ized water was used for the preparation of all aqueous solutions. The spectral data for the compound are as followed:

Microwave-induced reaction at low temperature: The polyaromatic imine **4** was prepared by condensing benzaldehyde with phenanthrenyl amine. To the polyaromatic imine **4** (100 mg, 0.26 mmol) was added dry dichloromethane (5 mL) and triethylamine (0.2 mL). The reaction mixture was cooled to -78°C in a bath of acetone and dry ice and to it was added a solution of the acetoxyacetyl chloride (0.4 mL) in dichloromethane (1 mL). The reaction mixture was then transferred to a domestic microwave oven and irradiated at low power setting (power level 3) for 1 h. However, the temperature was maintained by the addition of acetone and dry ice to the bath throughout the process. The reaction vessel was brought outside the microwave oven after each 15 min interval to maintain the temperature. After an hour, the reaction vessel was kept at room temperature for 15 min, it was then successively washed with sodium bicarbonate solution (5 mL), brine (5 mL), and water (5 mL). The organic layer was collected was dried with magnesium sulfate and evaporated to obtain the crude product as a *cis* isomer. The 3-acetoxy- β -lactam **6** was obtained as white crystalline solid (70 mg). It was characterized by IR and NMR data.

Compound 6: NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm): 8.37–8.34 (m, 4H), 7.67–7.65 (m, 4H), 7.50–7.46 (m, 2H), 7.35–7.27 (m, 4H), 7.35–7.27 (m, 4H), 5.95 (d, J 4.9 Hz, 1H), 5.43 (d, J 5.1 Hz, 1H), 2.14 (s, 6H); ^{13}C NMR (150 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm): 19.8 (2 CH_3), 61.6 (2CH), 76.5 (2OCH), 115.8 (2CH), 116.0 (CH), 123.7 (2CH), 126.4 (2CH), 126.9 (2CH), 127.0 (CH), 127.4 (CH), 127.5 (CH), 127.9 (2CH), 128.6 (2CH), 129.2 (2CH), 132.1 (4C), 135.0 (2 C), 161.9 (2C), 169.2 (2C=O), 170.0 (2C=O); IR ν_{max} , 1745.67 cm^{-1} (C=O).

Microwave-induced reaction at high temperature: The same amount of reagents and solvents were taken in a 125 mL Erlenmeyer flask at room temperature and the reaction mixture was placed in a domestic microwave oven. A beaker (250 mL) containing of water (100 mL) was placed next to the reaction mixture. The reaction mixture was irradiated for 5–7 min at low power keeping the temperature of the reaction at about 50°C . This was done by adjusting the amount of water in the beaker. There will be no boiling of the reaction mixture under this condition. Extraction and column chroma-

tography as described above afforded the *trans* product **7** (60 mg). The compound was characterized by IR and NMR data. It is better to use dichloroethane as a solvent for microwave-induced method to stop evaporation of the solvent.

Compound 7: As white solid, 40% NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm): 8.38–8.35 (m, 4H), 7.68–7.67 (m, 4H), 7.58–7.57 (m, 4H), 7.52–7.467 (m, 2H), 7.36–7.27 (m, 4H), 5.38 (d, J 1.6 Hz, 1H), 5.01 (d, J 1.7 Hz, 1H), 2.14 2.09 (s, 6H); ^{13}C NMR (150 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm): 20.5 (2 CH_3), 63.9 (2CH), 82.7 (2OCH), 116.0 (2CH), 117.3 (2CH), 123.7 (2CH), 127.3 (2CH), 127.3 (2CH), 128.9 (2CH), 129.2 (2CH), 129.3 (2CH), 129.5 (2CH), 130.5 (2CH), 132.1(C), 135.0 (C), 135.1 (2C), 161.9 (2C), 162.1 (2C), 169.2 (2C=O), 169.7 (2C=O); IR ν_{max} , 1745.67 cm^{-1} (C=O).

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